

A PROBABILISTIC PROOF THAT $\sum_{J=1}^N H_J^{(s)} = (N+1)H_N^{(s)} - H_N^{(s-1)}$

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Abstract

Let $H_n^{(s)}$ ($s \geq 0$) be the n th generalized harmonic number. In this note, we provide a probabilistic proof for the familiar sum identity $\sum_{j=1}^n H_j^{(s)} = (n+1)H_n^{(s)} - H_n^{(s-1)}$.

1. Introduction

The harmonic number H_n is defined to be the partial sum of the harmonic series, i.e.,

$$H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k}.$$

The first 10 terms of the sequence of harmonic numbers are

$$1, \frac{3}{2}, \frac{11}{6}, \frac{25}{12}, \frac{137}{60}, \frac{49}{20}, \frac{363}{140}, \frac{761}{280}, \frac{7129}{2520}, \frac{7381}{2520}.$$

Since the harmonic series diverges, it is clear that H_n can get arbitrarily large, although it does so quite slowly. For instance, some large harmonic numbers are

$$\begin{aligned} H_{1000000} &\approx 14.3927, \\ H_{2000000} &\approx 15.0858, \\ H_{3000000} &\approx 15.4913, \\ H_{4000000} &\approx 15.7790. \end{aligned}$$

Harmonic numbers are also defined in a more generalized form. The generalized harmonic numbers $H_n^{(s)}$ of order s are defined by

$$H_n^{(s)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k^s} \quad (s \geq 0).$$

Generalized harmonic numbers are also denoted by $H_{n,s}$. In the special case of $s = 0$ we have $H_n^{(0)} = n$, and the special case of $s = 1$ gives $H_n^{(1)} = H_n$.

Harmonic numbers satisfy many interesting properties. Greene and Knuth [2, p.10] listed some commonly used identities. One of them is the following well-known sum identity:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n H_j = (n + 1)H_n - n. \tag{1}$$

In general, this identity can be defined for generalized harmonic numbers as follows (see, e.g., [4, p. 853 and 856]):

$$\sum_{j=1}^n H_j^{(s)} = (n + 1)H_n^{(s)} - H_n^{(s-1)} \quad (s \geq 1). \tag{2}$$

Since $H_n^{(1)} = H_n$ and $H_n^{(0)} = n$, the Identity (2) gives Identity (1) when $s = 1$.

In this note, we will give a probabilistic proof of Identity (2). To this end, in subsequent sections, the following notation will be used: \mathbb{N} denotes the set of all natural numbers; $\Pr(X = x)$ denotes the probability mass function of a discrete random variable X ; and $E[X]$ denotes the expected value of the random variable X .

2. Zipfian Distribution (Zipf’s law)

A random variable X has the *Zipfian distribution* with parameters $s \geq 0$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, if its probability mass function is given by

$$\Pr(X = x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{x^s H_n^{(s)}} & \text{if } x \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

where $H_n^{(s)}$ is the n th generalized harmonic number of order s .

Usually, the shorthand $X \sim \text{Zipf}(s, n)$ is used to indicate that the random variable X has Zipfian distribution with parameters s and n . In simple terms, the Zipfian distribution predicts that out of a population of n elements, the frequency of rank x is given by (3), where s is the value of the exponent characterizing the distribution. This prediction is called Zipf’s law. For more details, see, for example, [1, p. 373].

3. Probabilistic Proof of Identity (2)

Proof of Identity (2). Let X be a random variable taking values among the non-negative integers. We recall the well-known tail sum formula for the expectation of

X (see, e.g., [3]), namely,

$$E[X] = \sum_{x=0}^{\infty} \Pr(X > x).$$

Since we have $E[X] = \sum_x x \Pr(X = x)$, the above identity may be written as

$$\sum_{x=0}^{\infty} x \Pr(X = x) = \sum_{x=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \sum_{y=0}^x \Pr(X = y) \right). \tag{4}$$

If X has support in $\{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, then Equation (4) gives

$$\begin{aligned} n + 1 &= \sum_{x=0}^n x \Pr(X = x) + \sum_{x=0}^n \sum_{y=0}^x \Pr(X = y) \\ &= \sum_{x=1}^n x \Pr(X = x) + \sum_{x=0}^n \sum_{y=0}^x \Pr(X = y). \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Now, suppose that X is a Zipfian random variable with parameters $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \geq 0$. By using the probability mass function of X (see (3)) and applying (5), we have (note that $\Pr(X = 0) = 0$)

$$n + 1 = \sum_{x=1}^n \frac{x}{x^s H_n^{(s)}} + \sum_{x=1}^n \sum_{y=1}^x \frac{1}{y^s H_n^{(s)}} = \frac{1}{H_n^{(s)}} \left(\sum_{x=1}^n \frac{1}{x^{s-1}} + \sum_{x=1}^n \sum_{y=1}^x \frac{1}{y^s} \right);$$

that is,

$$(n + 1)H_n^{(s)} = \sum_{x=1}^n \frac{1}{x^{s-1}} + \sum_{x=1}^n \sum_{y=1}^x \frac{1}{y^s} = H_n^{(s-1)} + \sum_{x=1}^n H_x^{(s)}.$$

This completes the proof. □

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